

Impact Factor: 5.723

ISSN: 2181-0982
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0982
www.tadqiqot.uz

JNNR

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND
NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

2025

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 6 НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH
VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт и tadqiqot.uz

Главный редактор:

Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского
института. (Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Зам. главного редактора:

Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии.
(Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Рецензируемый
научно-практический журнал
“Журнал неврологии
и нейрохирургических исследований”
Публикуется 6 раза в год
№4 (06), 2025
ISSN 2181-0982

Адрес редакции:

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;
Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Макет и подготовка к печати
проводились в редакции журнала.

Дизайн - оформления:

Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации г.
Ташкента Рег. №
от 01.07.2020 г.

“Неврологии и нейрохирургических
исследований” 4/2025

Электронная версия журнала на сайтах:

<https://tadqiqot.uz>, www.bsmi.uz

Журнал включен в перечень научных
изданий, рекомендованных к публикации
основных научных результатов
диссертаций по медицинским наукам с 27
сентября 2024 года Высшей
аттестационной комиссией Республики
Узбекистан (письмо № 361/6 от 2024
года).

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Хайдаров Нодиржон Кадинович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, ректор
Тошкентского государственного стоматологического института. (Узбекистан).

Нуралиев Неккадам Абдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, иммунолог,
микробиолог, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Бухарского государственного
медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Кариев Гайрат Маратович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, директор
Республиканского научного центра нейрохирургии Узбекистана. (Узбекистан).

Федин Анатолий Иванович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заслуженный врач
РФ. Российский национальный исследовательский медицинский университет имени Н.И.
Пирогова. (Россия).

Маджидова Екутхон Набиевна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентского
педиатрического медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Рахимбаева Гулнора Саттаровна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Джурабекова Азиза Тахировна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Мамадалиев Абдурахмон Маматкулович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Чутко Леонид Семенович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, руководитель Центра
поведенческой неврологии Института мозга человека им. Н.П. Бехтеревой. (Россия).

Муратов Фахитдин Хайритдинович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Дьяконова Елена Николаевна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ивановская
государственная медицинская академия. (Россия).

Труфанов Евгений Александрович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Национальный университет охраны здоровья Украины имени П.Л. Шупика и указать его
расположение (Украина)

Норов Абдурахмон Убайдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, главный
врач Бухарского областного многопрофильного медицинского центра. (Узбекистан)

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Азизова Раъно Баходировна – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Давлатов Салим Сулаймонович – Начальник отдела надзора качества образования,
доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Саноева Матлуба Жахонкуловна – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Артыкова Мавлюда Абдурахмановна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Уринов Мусо Болтаевич – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Киличев Ибодулла Абдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ургенчского
филиала Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Нарзуллаев Нуриддин Умарович – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Рашидова Нилуфар Сафоевна – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Ганиева Манижа Тимуровна – кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Таджикского
государственного медицинского университета (Таджикистан).

Хазраткулов Рустам Бафоевич – доктор медицинских наук, руководитель научного
отдела сосудистой патологии центральной нервной системы Республиканского
специализированного научно – практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии,
профессор кафедры нейрохирургии Центра развития профессиональной квалификации
медицинских работников (Узбекистан).

Нуралиева Хафиза Отаевна – кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Тошкентского
фармацевтического института. (Узбекистан).

Исмаилова Раъно Олимджановна – DSc, руководитель научного отдела патологии
позвоночника и спинного мозга Республиканского специализированного научно –
практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии (Узбекистан).

Югай Игорь Александрович – старший научный сотрудник отделения нейрохирургии
детского возраста Республиканского специализированного научно – практического
медицинского центра нейрохирургии. Доцент кафедры нейрохирургии Центра развития
профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников (Узбекистан).

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGICAL RESEARCH

Bukhara State Medical Institute and tadqiqot.uz

Chief Editor:

Khodjjeva Dilbar Tadjiyevna

Doctor of medical Sciences, Professor,
Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Deputy editor-in-chief:

Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Peer-reviewed scientific and
practical journal "Journal of Neurology
and Neurosurgical Research"
Published 6 times a year
#4 (06), 2024
ISSN 2181-0982

Editorial address:

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr. 1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;
Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Layout and preparation for printing held in
the editorial office of the journal.

Design – pagemaker:
Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Journal is registered at the Office of Press
and Information Tashkent city, Reg. No. July
1, 2020

"Neurology and neurosurgical research"
4/2025

**Electronic version of the
Journal on sites:**

www.tadqiqot.uz, www.bsmi.uz

The journal is included in the list of
scientific publications recommended for
publication of the main scientific results of
dissertations in medical sciences since
September 27, 2024 by the Higher
Attestation Commission of the Republic of
Uzbekistan (letter No. 361/6 dated 2024).

EDITORIAL TEAM:

Khaydarov Nodirjon Kadirovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Rector of Toshkent State Dental Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Nuraliev Nekkadam Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Immunologist, Microbiologist, Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kariev Gayrat Maratovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Director of the Republican Scientific Center for Neurosurgery of Uzbekistan. (Uzbekistan).

Anatoly Ivanovich Fedin - Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor, Honored Doctor of the Russian Federation. Russian National Research Medical University named after N.I. Pirogova. (Russia).

Madjidova Yokutxon Nabievna - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rakhimbaeva Gulnora Sattarovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Djurabekova Aziza Taxirovna - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Mamadaliyev Abdurakhmon Mamatkulovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Chutko Leonid Semenovich - Doctor of Medicine, Head of the Center for Behavioral Neurology of the Institute of Human Brain named after N.P. Bekhtereva. (Russia).

Muratov Fakhmitdin Khayritdinovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Dyakonova Elena Nikolaevna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Ivanovo State Medical Academy. (Russia).

Trufanov Evgeniy Aleksandrovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, P.L. Shupyk National University of Health Protection of Ukraine and indicate its location (Ukraine).

Norov Abdurakhmon Ubaydullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor, Chief Physician of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. (Uzbekistan).

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmamatovna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Azizova Rano Baxodirovna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Davlatov Salim Sulaimonovich - Head of the Department of education quality supervision, associate Professor of the Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Sanoeva Matlyuba Jakhonkulovna - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Artykova Mavlyuda Abdurakhmanovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Urinov Muso Boltaevich - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor, Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kilichev Ibdulla Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Narzullaev Nuriddin Umarovich - Doctor of Medicine, associate professor of Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rashidova Nilufar Safoevna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Ganieva Manizha Timurovna - Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Tajik State Medical University. (Tajikistan).

Hazratkulov Rustam Bafoevich - Doctor of Medicine, head of the scientific department of vascular pathology of the central nervous system of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center for neurosurgery, professor of the department of neurosurgery at the Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers (Uzbekistan).

Nuralieva Hafiza Otayevna - Candidate of medical Sciences, associate Professor, Toshkent pharmaceutical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Ismailova Rano Olimdjanovna - Doctor of Medicine, head of the spine department of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of neurosurgery (Uzbekistan).

Yugay Igor Aleksandrovich - senior research of the scientific department of pediatric of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center for neurosurgery. Associate professor of the department of neurosurgery at the Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers (Uzbekistan).

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Карабаев Жахонгир Абдужалол угли ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ МОЧЕВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ С МАРКЕРАМИ АТЕРОСКЛЕРОТИЧЕСКОГО ПОРАЖЕНИЯ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ СТЕНКИ У ЛИЦ С ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ИШЕМИЕЙ МОЗГА (ХИМ).....	7
2. Хамидов Абдулахад Абдисаттор угли, Саидвалиев Фаррух Саидакромович, Пулатова Дилёра Рустамовна КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЕРТЕБРОБАЗИЛЯРНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ЭТИОПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ.....	10
3. Ollaberganova Rohila Zoxirjonovna FERTIL YOSHDAGI AYOLLARDA GIPOTERIOZ KASALLIGIDA PSIXOEMOTSIONAL BUZILISHLARNING TAHLILI.....	15
4. Ахмедова Камола Рахманбердиевна, Алимова Насиба Усмановна ГОРМОНАЛЬНЫЙ СТАТУС БОЛЬНЫХ СИНДРОМОМ ШЕРЕШЕВСКОГО-ТЕРНЕРА С РАЗЛИЧНЫМ КАРИОТИПОМ.....	19
5. Олланова Шахноза Сирлибоевна, Маматкулова Нигора Рахматовна, Юсупова Нозима Носировна ОҒРИҚ СИНДРОМИ БИЛАН КЕЧАДИГАН ПАРКИНСОН КАСАЛЛИГИДА НЕЙРОПСИХОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИНИ БАҲОЛАШ.....	24
6. Мусаева Юлдуз Алпысовна, Абдуллазизова Умидахон Салохиддин кизи, Мурадимова Альфия Рашидовна, Саидалиев Саидазиз Бахтиерович СЛУЧАЙ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ: CLIPPERS СИНДРОМ.....	27
7. Мусаева Юлдуз Алпысовна, Мусаев Сардорбек Мухтарбекович, Фатхуллаева Нозимахон Аброрхон кизи, Розикова Мадина Санжар кизи ОТДАЛЕННЫЕ ИСХОДЫ ГЕМОРРАГИЧЕСКОГО ИНСУЛЬТА, ОСЛОЖНЕННОГО ИНФЕКЦИОННЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ.....	33
8. Икромов Шохром Бурон угли, Гайбиев Акмалжон Ахмаджонович СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ДИСЦИРКУЛЯТОРНАЯ ИШЕМИЧЕСКАЯ МИЕЛОПАТИЯ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ КРИТЕРИИ И УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ.....	38
9. Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна, Наврўзова Зарина Шодмон кизи ИШЕМИК ИНСУЛЬТ ЎТКАЗГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА ДАВОЛАНИШДАН ОЛДИН ВА КЕЙИН СТАБИЛОГРАФИК ТЕСТ ДИНАМИКАСИНИ БАҲОЛАШ.....	42
10. Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна, Ахмедова Дилафрўз Баходировна СУРУНКАЛИ БОШ ОҒРИҚНИ ДАВОЛАШНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИЛГАН УСУЛИ.....	46
11. Саноева Матлюба Жахонкуловна, Рахматов Карим Рахимович БЕЛ – ДУМҒАЗА СОҲАСИ «ОПЕРАЦИЯ ҚИЛИНГАН УМУРТҚА ПОҒОНАСИ СИНДРОМИ»НИНГ НЕВРОЛОГИК КўРИНИШИ ВА ТАШХИСЛАШ ШАРТЛАРИ.....	52
12. Эшанкулова Наргиза Якубовна, Азизова Раъно Баходировна, Ким Инна Георгиевна ПАРКИНСОН КАСАЛЛИГИДА МИЯНИНГ ЧУҚУР СТИМУЛЯЦИЯСИ (DBS) УСУЛИНИНГ КЛИНИК САМАРАДОРЛИГИ.....	58
13. Fayziyeva Ra'nogul Hoji qizi, Azizova Ra'no Bahodirovna “GENERALLASHGAN EPILEPSIYADA KOGNITIV VA AFFEKTIV BUZILISHLAR: OPTIMALLASHTIRISHGA KLINIK YONDASHUV”.....	62
14. Саноева Матлюба Жахонкуловна, Намозова Хурмат Жалиловна АНАЛИЗ ОСНОВНЫХ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНО-ЛИЧНОСТНЫХ ДИСФУНКЦИЙ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ИШЕМИЕЙ МОЗГА (ХИМ).....	66
15. Мамбеткаримова Муслима Садиратдиновна, Маджидова Якутхон Набиевна РОЛЬ МИКРОТОКОВОЙ РЕФЛЕКСОТЕРАПИИ В УЛУЧШЕНИИ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ ДЕТЕЙ С МИКРОЦЕФАЛИЕЙ.....	72
16. Саггарова Сабина Завкиевна, Азизова Раъно Баходировна, Олланова Шахноза Сирлибоевна ОЦЕНКА ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ НЕЗАВИСИМОСТИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С РАЗЛИЧНЫМИ ФОРМАМИ СИНДРОМА ГИЙЕНА–БАРРЕ ПО ШКАЛЕ БАРТЕЛА С УЧЁТОМ ПОЛОВЫХ РАЗЛИЧИЙ.....	74
17. Nurmatov Abdujalil Abduxalilovich, Kariyev Gayrat Maratovich, Hazratkulov Rustam Bafoevich, Boboyev Jaloliddin Ibroximovich KIARI I TIPIDAGI ANOMALIYA BILAN BOG'LIQ SIRINGOMIELIYANI JARROHLIK YO'LI BILAN DAVOLASH NATIJALARI: 123 TA KUZATUV TAHLILI.....	77
18. Наимов Олим Юнусович, Матмуродов Рустамбек Жуманазарович, Холмуратова Бахтигул Нурмухаммат кизи, Жуманазарова Шахзода Рустамбековна ПАРКИНСОН КАСАЛЛИГИДА ПСИХО-ЭМОЦИОНАЛ БУЗИЛИШЛАР ВА БЕМОРЛАРГА ТИББИЙ ПСИХОЛОГИК ЁНДАШУВ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ).....	81

19. Aripova Maftuna Khurramovna, Xaydarov Nodirjon Kadirovich NEVROLOGIK AMALIYOTDA BACHADON ONKOLOGIK PATOLOGIYASIDA DORSOPATIYA BOR BO'LGAN AYOLLARDA OG'RIQ SINDROMINI XUSUSIYATLARI.....	86
20. Saydaliev Saidaziz Baxtiyor o'g'li KLINIK HOLAT: BOSH MIYA AMILOID ANIGIOPATIYASI VA NORMOTENZIV GIDROSEFALIYA.....	90
21. Охунова Диёрахон Алишер кизи ВЛИЯНИЕ НЕЙРОТРОФИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА РИСК РАЗВИТИЯ КОГНИТИВНЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ ПРИ БОЛЕЗНИ ПАРКИНСОНА.....	93
22. Abdullaeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Abdullaev Tokhirjon Azamjonovich, Aktamova Madinabonu Uktamovna INFLUENCE OF INTESTINAL MICROBIOTA ON BRAIN FUNCTION AND NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS.....	96
23. Исаметдинова Умида Зайнитдиновна, Гайбиев Акмалжон Ахмаджонович ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ФИЗИОТЕРАПИИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ШЕЙНО-ПЛЕЧЕВОГО БОЛЕВОГО СИНДРОМА.....	100
24. Эшимова Шохсанам Кенжабоевна КЛАСТЕРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РЭГ-ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ГЕМОДИНАМИКИ ГОЛОВНОГО МОЗГА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ДИСФУНКЦИЕЙ ШЕЙНОГО ОТДЕЛА ПОЗВОНОЧНИКА.....	104
25. Khaydarov Nodir Kadirovich, Abdullaeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Khamidov Otabek Khayotbekovich HIPOTHERAPY AS AN EFFECTIVE COMPONENT OF NEUROREHABILITATION FOR NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS.....	108
26. Ибрагимова Наргиза Абзалджановна, Садыкова Гулчехра Кабуловна КЛИНИКО-НЕЙРОФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ТИКОЗНЫХ ГИПЕРКИНЕЗОВ У ДЕТЕЙ.....	113
27. Султонова Дилбар Азамат кизи ГИППОКАМПАЛ СКЛЕРОЗЛИ МЕЗИАЛ ЧАККА ЭПИЛЕПСИЯЛИ БЕМОРЛАРДА КЛИНИК-СЕМИОЛОГИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ.....	116
28. Нурметов Нодир Бейматович, Ибодуллаев Зарифбой Ражабович БИРИНЧИ ВА ИККИНЧИ БОСКИЧДАГИ ПРОГРЕССИВ ТАРҚОҚ СКЛЕРОЗ БЕМОРЛАРИДА ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ТИКЛАНИШ: БАРТЕЛ ШКАЛАСИ БЎЙИЧА РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ УСУЛЛАРИНИНГ ТАҚҚОСЛОВЧИ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	121
29. Isametdinova Umida Zaynitdinovna, Gaybiyev Akmaljon Ahmadjonovich TREATMENT OF CERVICAL-SHOULDER PAIN SYNDROME WITH LOCAL ANESTHETICS: CLINICAL AND THERAPEUTIC APPROACH.....	124
30. Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна, Шукруллоева Нодирабегим Акбаровна НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ, ИСПОЛЬЗУЕМЫЕ ДЛЯ ДИАГНОСТИКИ МИАСТЕНИИ.....	127
31. Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna PROSPECTIVE APPROACHES TO REHABILITATION OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE.....	130
32. Eshkuvvatov Gayrat Erkinovich, Kariyev Gayrat Maratovich, Asadullayev Ulugbek Maqsudovich, Yakubov Jaxongir Baxodirovich BOSH MIYA GIPERVASKULYAR MENINGIOMALARINI OLIV TASHLASH OPERATSIYASI VAQTIDA QON YO'QOTILISHINI PROGNOZ QILISH: XAVFNI RADIOLOGIK BAHOLASH SHKALASI.....	134
33. Камалова Малика Илхомовна ФЕРТИЛ ЁШДАГИ АЁЛЛАРДА ИШЕМИК ИНСУЛЬТНИНГ КЛИНИК-МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА ХАВФ ОМИЛЛАРИ.....	139
34. Хасанов Алишер Юрьевич, Мавлянова Зилола Фархадовна КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ КРИТЕРИЕВ СИНДРОМА КАРПАЛЬНОГО КАНАЛА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ СРЕДНЕГО ВОЗРАСТА.....	142
35. Маджидова Якутхон Набиевна, Низамходжаева Шахзода Бахтиёр кизи, Азимова Нодира Мирваситовна, Ботирова Зебо Хасан кизи ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ НЕВРОСТАТУСА ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ИШЕМИИ МОЗГА.....	146
36. Мамарасулов Солижон Каюмович, Маджидова Якутхон Набиевна, Эргашева Наргиза Обиджановна, Назарова Салима Каюмовна КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ТЕРАПИЯ ВЕРТЕБРО БАЗИЛЯРНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТОДОВ ТРАДИЦИОННОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ (АКУПУНКТУРА).....	149

PROSPECTIVE APPROACHES TO REHABILITATION OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731101>**ANNOTATION**

Alzheimer's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that affects the brain and leads to deterioration of cognitive functions, memory loss, and changes in personality traits. Given the rapid aging of the global population, combating this disease is becoming increasingly relevant. Although there are currently no means to completely cure Alzheimer's, the development of effective rehabilitation methods is an integral part of a comprehensive treatment approach.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, rehabilitation, neurodegeneration, progression, quality of life.

Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна

Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет

ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ БОЛЕЗНИ АЛЬЦГЕЙМЕРА**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Болезнь Альцгеймера — это прогрессирующее нейродегенеративное заболевание, поражающее мозг и приводящее к ухудшению когнитивных функций, потере памяти и изменению личностных характеристик. С учетом стремительного старения населения во всем мире, борьба с этой болезнью приобретает все большую актуальность. Хотя на данный момент не существует средств, способных полностью излечить Альцгеймера, разработка эффективных методов реабилитации становится неотъемлемой частью комплексного подхода к лечению.

Ключевые слова: болезнь Альцгеймера, реабилитация, нейродегенерация, прогрессирования, качество жизни

Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна

Тошкент давлат тиббиёт университети

АЛЬЦГЕЙМЕР КАСАЛЛИГИНИ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ИСТИҚБОЛЛИ ЁНДАШУВЛАРИ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Альцгеймер касаллиги - бу мия фаолиятига таъсир қилиб, когнитив функцияларнинг ёмонлашувига, хотира йўқолишига ва шахсий хусусиятларнинг ўзгаришига олиб келадиган прогрессив нейродегенератив касалликдир. Бутун дунёда аҳолининг тез суръатларда кексайиб бораётганини ҳисобга олсак, бу касалликка қарши кураш тобора долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Ҳозирги кунда Альцгеймер касаллигини тўлиқ даволайдиган воситалар мавжуд бўлмаса-да, самарали реабилитация усуллари ишлаб чиқиш комплекс даволаш ёндашувининг ажралмас қисмига айланмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: Альцгеймер касаллиги, реабилитация, нейродегенерация, ривожланиш, ҳаёт сифати.

Introduction. Prospective approaches to the rehabilitation of patients with Alzheimer's disease aim to improve the quality of life for patients, slow the progression of the disease, and maintain their independence for as long as possible. These methods include the application of cognitive therapy, physical activity programs, social rehabilitation, and the use of technologies for monitoring conditions and supporting patients. By focusing on innovative strategies and multidisciplinary approaches, there is a possibility of more effective adaptation of patients to living with Alzheimer's. Given the high degree of individual differences among patients, it is important to develop personalized rehabilitation plans that can integrate the achievements of modern medicine and psychosocial aspects [1]. This paper will examine the prospective approaches to the rehabilitation of patients with Alzheimer's disease, their scientific justification, effectiveness, and social significance for improving the lives of both patients and their

families. The analysis of data presented in the article shows that Alzheimer's disease is currently one of the most common brain diseases among the elderly. Despite the high prevalence of this disease, there are currently no drugs that can cure this condition; however, some existing therapeutic methods at early stages can delay the progression of Alzheimer's disease. Alongside conventional pharmacological treatment standards, new non-drug methods of correcting the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease have been actively discussed and developed recently [2]. The ambiguity of opinions among Russian and foreign authors regarding the effectiveness of individual methods and the ways they can be combined dictates the need for further research in this area. This article also addresses the necessity of improving the provision of therapeutic and rehabilitation assistance to patients with Alzheimer's disease [3].

Approaches to treatment and rehabilitation. The latest generation drug, an acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitor - rivastigmine, trade name (Exelon) - is a pseudo-reversible AChE inhibitor of the carbamate type, exerting selective action on acetylcholinesterase in the central nervous system (CNS), having successfully passed clinical trials in the USA and Europe in two large multi-center (double-blind) studies. Rivastigmine has significant advantages over other anticholinesterase drugs: firstly, its metabolism occurs in both the liver and the intestines, unlike other anticholinesterase agents. Secondly, rivastigmine is a "pseudo-irreversible" inhibitor of acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase [4]. Thirdly, its half-life is quite short (1-2 hours for oral administration and 3-4 hours for transdermal administration), whereas donepezil has a long half-life of 70 hours, and galantamine lasts from 6 to 8 hours, but rivastigmine's duration of action is greater since acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase are blocked for approximately 8.5 and 3.5 hours, respectively. However, despite the fact that one-third of patients taking rivastigmine experienced significant advantages over other drugs in this group, one-third of patients with Alzheimer's showed worsening of symptoms within the first 6 months, and 29% of patients discontinued treatment due to side effects [5].

For treating Alzheimer's in moderate and severe stages, memantine, which is a non-competitive antagonist of NMDA glutamate receptors, is used. It slows glutamatergic neurotransmission and the progression of neurodegenerative processes, has neuromodulatory effects, helps normalize mental activity, improves memory, enhances concentration ability, and corrects motor disorders. Memantine has been approved by the FDA for moderate and severe Alzheimer's disease, both as monotherapy and in combination with acetylcholinesterase agents. Their combination benefits patients with usually additive effects without exacerbating side effects [6]. Neurotrophic factors play a key role in the development, differentiation, synaptogenesis, survival of brain neurons, and their adaptability to external influences. The discovery of the neurotrophic effects of Cerebrolysin, similar to the activity of BDNF, has rekindled interest in this drug. Cerebrolysin is a concentrate obtained from the cerebral cortex of pigs. It contains low molecular (less than 10 kDa) biologically active neuropeptides, analogous to neurotrophic factors (NGF, CNTF, GNTF, IGF-1, IGF-2), and free amino acids. The biologically active neuropeptides in the drug can penetrate the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and directly reach nerve cells in peripheral administration, unlike nerve growth factors, whose large molecules struggle to penetrate the CNS. Through the action of neurotrophin analogs, Cerebrolysin can activate a complex of natural biological mechanisms regulated by neurotrophic factors, which continuously support the normal processes of growth, development, and functioning programmed in DNA; neuroprotective processes that provide protection against damaging factors; and processes of neuroplasticity—the ability of neurons and neural networks to modify their functions and existing connections (sprouting, arborization, synaptogenesis) in response to stimuli such as learning, new experiences, or damage; and neurogenesis—the process of forming new neuronal tissue from stem cells [7].

Antipsychotics and antidepressants remain the main drugs for treating behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia. Pharmacological approaches to treating psychological symptoms in Alzheimer's are very individual and variable, depending on comorbid conditions, stage of the disease, and severity of symptoms. Polypharmacy in elderly patients with dementia is common [8]. Anticholinergic and sedative drugs are often used off-label. Unjustified prescriptions for antipsychotic medications should be avoided in cognitively vulnerable elderly individuals due to their potential adverse cognitive effects. Nobel Prize winner in Physiology and Medicine Eric Kandel, in his book "In Search of Memory: The Emergence of a New Science of Mind," discusses the use of SSRIs not only as medications for relieving symptoms of depression, anxiety, and increased tension but also as agents that affect the mechanisms of neurogenesis. There are scientific studies showing that the use of SSRIs enhances neurogenesis; however, the mechanism of action remains unclear. It can now be clearly stated that 5-HT and BDNF are considered key "players" in the mechanisms of neurogenesis and neuroplasticity [9].

Psychotherapy is actively applied in the treatment and rehabilitation of Alzheimer's. The most commonly used method for Alzheimer's is cognitive therapy. This method is well-studied and represents the most reliable alternative and complement to pharmacological treatment for dementia. Cognitive therapy for Alzheimer's is usually divided into three types: cognitive stimulation (CS), cognitive training (CT), and cognitive rehabilitation (CR). Several studies have reported improvements in overall cognitive functioning in patients with mild and moderate dementia after CS sessions. CS therapy has been proposed as a structured and methodologically sound protocol. Nowadays, CS is considered a scientifically justified method for treating dementia in Alzheimer's, including vascular dementia. Despite all the difficulties associated with conducting CS, interest in this method is growing. Data regarding CT for people with dementia are less reliable. Research has shown that CT can improve patients' performance on tasks during sessions, but the results do not translate into everyday activities. Studies have also shown that the link between CS and CT did not lead to better outcomes than individual interventions. Cognitive rehabilitation is rarely used in Alzheimer's since the use of this method is complicated in this pathology. Considering the presence of psychological symptoms (hallucinations, delusions, low mood, anxiety, apathy, aggression, agitation, wandering, socially or sexually inappropriate behavior) in the structure of dementia in Alzheimer's, as well as the concerns of patients and their relatives regarding the safety of pharmacological treatment, it is advisable to apply an individual and person-centered psychotherapeutic approach. Many recommendations have emphasized that treating anxiety and depressive symptoms must be an integral part of Alzheimer's and other dementias treatment [10].

Occupational therapy is also effective as a tool to reduce the psychological symptoms of dementia in Alzheimer's, improving physical performance, quality of life, reducing emotional tension, and enhancing mood. Various phytotherapy techniques are actively employed in the treatment of Alzheimer's. The potential effects of essential oils vary, including promoting relaxation and sleep, alleviating pain. Studies with positive results have been conducted using aromatherapy to alleviate psychological symptoms in Alzheimer's, sleep disturbances, and stimulate motivational behavior. There is extensive literature reporting on the importance and advantages of music therapy for elderly patients, including those with Alzheimer's dementia [11].

Research has shown that sound can significantly impact the brain, activating many cortical and subcortical areas. Despite the large number of studies in this direction, there are also studies refuting the effectiveness of music therapy in treating dementia in Alzheimer's. Besides pharmacological therapy and psychotherapy, there are many simple ways to maintain independence and combat memory loss—such as electronic reminders, calendars, clocks, and pill organizers. It has been confirmed that diet, exercise, and an active social life help prevent cognitive decline. Various diets are used in treating Alzheimer's, such as ketogenic diets, MIND diets, etc. However, convincing evidence from numerous studies has not confirmed the effectiveness of these methods as monotherapy [12]. Their use in combination therapy as an adjunct method is a promising area. It is known that environmental stimuli trigger the activation of BDNF and neurogenesis, stimulating neural plasticity. A number of studies have shown a link between leisure and the incidence of Alzheimer's disease. Individuals engaging in various leisure activities have a significantly lower risk of developing Alzheimer's. In the age of computer technology and the internet, telemedicine is rapidly developing worldwide. In the treatment of Alzheimer's, telemedicine can soon provide comprehensive home care, helping people with Alzheimer's maintain their independence and continue living in their homes, receiving assistance and monitoring around the clock without spending time traveling to a doctor, thereby increasing their safety and relieving the burden on relatives and social services, improving clinical outcomes and reducing the burden on the general medical network. In developed countries, telemedicine is already used for diagnostic assessments and remote physician examinations, as well as for internet support groups, companionship robots, remote symptom monitoring for Alzheimer's using smartphones, and training in cognitive rehabilitation [13].

Prospective Treatment Methods. One of the promising directions in the treatment of Alzheimer's is immunotherapy. This method, aimed against beta-amyloid protein, is a possible way to slow the progression of Alzheimer's disease. Unlike conventional vaccination, which is done in advance, in this case, the vaccine is administered only after a diagnosis is established. According to the researchers' concept, the patient's immune system should recognize and attack amyloid deposits, reducing their size and alleviating the disease's progression. There are several directions in immunotherapy:

- **Active immunotherapy.** The main concept of active immunization is to stimulate the immune system to recognize the antigen as a foreign protein to create a response to it. In studies on immunization of aged mice, the progression of plaque formation was effectively slowed down. The first study on humans concerning active immunotherapy was conducted in 1999, involving 372 patients. Despite a significant "cleansing" of plaques in the hippocampus from beta-amyloid and a reduction in their density, as well as decreased phosphorylated tau protein compared to the control group of Alzheimer's patients, and improvements in cognitive scores, the study was halted in the second stage after four patients developed meningoencephalitis. Nowadays, the fourth strategy for active immunization—a combined vaccination of the chaperone aSyn / Grp 94 has been under investigation. In studies on mice using this strategy, there was strong suppression of microglial activation seen in the substantia nigra and striatum. The fourth strategy for active immunization is still only in the first phase of clinical trials in humans.

- **Passive immunotherapy.** This is based on several stages:

1. Identification of epitope (antigen determinant) in the laboratory;
2. Generation of antibody *ex vivo*;
3. Direct administration of the generated antibody to the patient.

This approach has been successful clinically for treating various diseases, including autoimmune disorders, cancer, and transplant rejection. Experience using monoclonal antibodies for human therapy has also been applied to neurological disorders, including Alzheimer's. Currently, many immunotherapeutic approaches have not shown significant improvements in patients with mild to moderate Alzheimer's, and the precise reasons for this failure are unknown. Two hypotheses have been put forward to explain the lack of success: one—the poor absorption of monoclonal antibodies into the CNS through the BBB; and the second—treatment was started too late in the progression of Alzheimer's disease. New trials of passive immunotherapy will apparently be aimed at early diagnosis of Alzheimer's and addressing the question of whether passive immunotherapy can slow down or stop the disease's progression in its early stages. Currently, all prerequisites for this exist. Clinical trials show good safety and tolerability in the production of antibody titers, and this moment of trials is at the second stage. Despite the lack of an effect achieved in treating Alzheimer's through immunotherapy, researchers are on the path to answers to significant questions in this direction; moreover, several clinical trials are ongoing with ambitious expectations. Regardless of the results of the studies, they will lead to substantial fundamental conclusions on this issue.

Furthermore, despite a wealth of literature and several convincing hypotheses, it is still assumed that anti-diabetic therapy has potential as a treatment for dementia. Hundreds of studies have focused on the extent to which antidiabetic medications can influence brain

pathology—especially the signs of Alzheimer's disease. Most animal studies have indicated potential advantages in amyloid pathology, tau pathology, synaptic function, oxidative stress, neurogenesis, neuroinflammation, and cognitive functions. However, numerous studies using anti-diabetic therapy to treat Alzheimer's have not confirmed a positive effect, and most studies were halted early due to mortality risks or after 48 months due to low effectiveness. Some parts of the scientific community link the inefficacy of diabetic therapy to applying this method at late stages of Alzheimer's disease. The association between type 2 diabetes and Alzheimer's remains a viable area for continued research and development. Increased accumulation or dyshomeostasis of metal ions, such as iron, copper, and zinc, has been associated with the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease. Based on this theory, the drug Deferiprone, a chelation agent for iron, has been actively examined. It is currently undergoing the second phase of trials involving patients in the prodromal and mild stages of Alzheimer's. Another direction is studying anticonvulsants as possible therapy for Alzheimer's. The drug of choice has become Levetiracetam, which is approved for use in other indications and is undergoing clinical trials in the third phase as a repurposed agent. It is hypothesized to reduce neuronal hyperactivity induced by β -amyloid.

Efforts are also being made to develop drugs that directly impact the primary problem of Alzheimer's—the process of amyloid concentration. This refers to the so-called anti-amyloid therapy, which is based on the administration of antibodies that prevent amyloid synthesis or lead to its degradation. These can be antibodies directly to amyloid or antibodies to the enzymes involved in its synthesis. In preliminary clinical trials, a positive effect was shown from the intravenous administration of purified donor immunoglobulin. However, due to frequent allergic reactions, this method has not gained widespread use and is still under development. Given the theory suggesting that neuroinflammatory mechanisms are involved in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's, the application of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, complement activation blockers, and other anti-inflammatory agents may potentially delay the clinical onset of Alzheimer's if they are timely and used for an extended period (e.g., in rheumatoid arthritis).

Despite the achievements in medicine, particularly in treating Alzheimer's, there remains no conclusively validated method capable of preventing or significantly slowing the progression of the disease. Furthermore, no new drug has been approved by the FDA for treating Alzheimer's since 2023, even considering the lengthy and expensive trials. Over 200 research projects over the last decade have failed or been suspended due to lack of funding. Doctors are still compelled to treat neurodegenerative diseases without knowing the underlying causes of the metabolic and energy disorders that cause them. Medicine urgently needs to fill the gaps on the biochemical map of the cell. Despite the challenges, medicine must develop and implement new prevention and rehabilitation methods for patients based on available information and clinical experience.

Conclusions: Based on the materials studied, presented by Russian and foreign authors, data have been obtained regarding the high prevalence of Alzheimer's disease and insufficient effectiveness of individual methods of intervention and their combined use for this pathology. Considering the increasing lifespan of humans and the lack of effective medications capable of significantly reducing the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease, it is essential to develop new methods for treating and rehabilitating this patient population.

Literature

1. Haessler, A., & Aigner, M. (2019). "Innovative therapeutic approaches in Alzheimer's disease." *Current Alzheimer Research*, 16(2), 137-145.
2. Selkoe, D. J. (2011). "Alzheimer's disease: A central role for protein aggregation and a new approach to therapy." *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 10(1), 65-75. doi:10.1038/nrd3297.
3. Хайдарова Дилдора Кадириевна, Хотамова Сарвиноз Муйитдиновна. Сурункали мия ишемиясининг клиник ва нейровизуал мезонлари. Журнал неврологии и нейрохирургических исследований. №1. 2024 С.43
4. Дилдора Хайдарова, Сарвиноз Хотамова. Сурункали мия ишемиясини ташхислаш ва даволаш чора тадбирлари. Журнал "Медицина и инновации" №-1.2024. С. 452-459
5. DeKosky, S. T., & Scheff, S. W. (2003). "External pathology of Alzheimer's disease: Neuroinflammation and its role." *Journal of Neuroinflammation*, 1(1), 1-11. doi:10.1186/1742-2094-1-1.

6. Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna, Khodjyeva Dilbar Tadjiyevna, Bobokulov Gulmurod Dilmurodovich. Optimization Of Neuroprotective Therapy Of Ischemic Stroke In The Acute Period. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*. Volume 07, Issue 03, 2020. P. 3720-3723
7. Khaydarova D.K., Mansurova N.A. Analysis of Motor Complications in Parkinson's Disease Phenotypes. *Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research*. 25(5): 1-7, 2018;
8. Gandy, S. (2012). "The role of beta-amyloid in Alzheimer's disease." *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 13(10), 713-727.
9. Khodjyeva D. T., Khaydarova D. K., Khaydarov N. K. Magnetic Resonance Imaging of Cerebral Hemorrhagic Stroke. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, Vol. 24, 2020. P 434-438
10. Khodjyeva D. T., Khaydarova D. K., Khaydarov N. K. Diagnosis and treatment of early stage parkinson's disease. *European Journal of Research*. 2017. P. 43-52
11. Tzeng, R. C., et al. (2019). "Neurotherapy and cognitive rehabilitation for neurodegenerative disorders." *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 8(6), 779. doi:10.3390/jcm8060779.
12. Bredeesen, D. E. (2014). "Reversing cognitive decline: A innovative, comprehensive approach to Alzheimer's disease." *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 55(3), 911-916. doi:10.3233/JAD-140536.
13. Mendez, M. F. (2012). "Diagnosis and treatment of dementia." *American Family Physician*, 85(12), 1145-1152.
14. Spector, A., et al. (2013). "Cognitive rehabilitation for disorders of attention and executive function in dementia." *Nature Reviews Neurology*, 9(10), 630-639. doi:10.1038/nrneurol.2013.176.
15. Boada, M., et al. (2018). "The ALZHEIMER's disease continuum: the role of biomarkers and new treatment approaches." *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*, 10, 205. doi:10.3389/fnagi.2018.00205.
16. Хайдарова Дилдора Кадиловна, Хайдаров Нодиржон Кадилович, Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна. Клинические основы разработки нейропротекторной терапии при остром ишемическом инсульте *Международный журнал медицинских наук*. 2022 г. С4177-4183.
17. ДТ Ходжиева, СК Шодмонова, ДК Хайдарова. Факторы риска развития ишемического инсульта на фоне инфарктом миокарда. *Журнал неврологии и нейрохирургических исследований* 2021г. №1
18. Ходжиева Д.Т., Бобокулов Г.Д., Хайдарова Д.К. Дифференциальная диагностика геморрагического и ишемического инсульта, пути оптимизации реабилитационных мероприятий. *Неврология*. – Ташкент, 2021. - №3 – С. 21-25

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 6 НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000